

The Effect of Optical Fibre Cross-Sectional Shape and Microstructure on Out-of-Plane Strain Sensitivity in Flexible Photonic Sensors

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Background and motivation

FBG in standard fibre

FBG in polarisation maintaining fibre

Motivation

- CFRP strain monitoring often uses FBGs in standard circular fibre.
- These detect in-plane strain well, but not through-thickness strains critical in delamination, matrix cracking.
- Polarisation-maintaining fibres can detect out of plane strains through birefringent response, but...
- Circular geometry twists, making direction of strain ambiguous - $\theta = ?$.

Objective

- Create orientation-stable, birefringent sensors that can resolve in-plane and out-of-plane strains.
- Enabling comprehensive 3D strain mapping during both manufacturing and in-service use of CFRPs.

Prior Work: 3D Strain Sensing - FHD planar chips

Approach: Uses a strain–optic matrix (K-matrix) derived from first principles of the photoelastic effect.

Formulation: Based on spectral shifts in TE and TM polarisations of two orthogonal waveguides:

Limitations:

- Chip-based fabrication is not scalable for long sensor lengths.
- Difficult to integrate into continuous optical fibre networks.
- Coupling to fibre and embedding chips remain complex and fragile.

$$\frac{\Delta\lambda_i}{\lambda_i} = \sum_j K_{ij}\epsilon_j$$

Where:

- $\frac{\Delta\lambda_i}{\lambda_i}$: Normalized wavelength shift in mode i (e.g., TE or TM).
- K_{ij} : Elements of the strain–optic sensitivity matrix (based on waveguide orientation and photoelastic constants).
- ϵ_j : Strain components $\epsilon_x, \epsilon_y, \epsilon_z$

CFRP tensile tests: measured strain comparison

Sensor fabrication – Flat fibres

Key innovations – enable scalability and integration

Laser powder deposition of waveguides

- Precise placement of doped silica cores on flat preforms
- Avoids the need for traditional MCVD or lithographic patterning.
- Flexible core design: refractive index, geometry, and number of cores can be tuned.

Rectangular Preform Design & Stack-and-Draw

- Rectangular in cross-section → high aspect ratio final fibre.
- Compatible with standard fibre draw towers → scalable production.

Incorporation of Internal Microstructure

- Microstructures such as air channels can be embedded → tune birefringence

Femtosecond Laser Post-Processing

- Enables fine-tuning of waveguide paths or inscription of Bragg gratings.
- Multi-core patterning or localised index modifications.

Laser powder deposition

P. Maniewski, B. Moog, M. Whittaker, *Proc. of SPIE*, Vol. 13356 1335606-1

Stack and draw

Femtosecond laser writing

T. Lee, P. Maniewski, M. Whittaker, B. Moog, M. Beresna, C. Holmes, *Proc. of SPIE*, Vol. 13639 136396V-4

Sensor optimisation

What determines sensitivity?:

- “The degree to which the birefringence of the waveguide changes in response to through thickness strains”

- Birefringence governed by principal strains ($\epsilon_{33} - \epsilon_{22}$)

$$B = n_2 - n_3 = \frac{n_0^3}{2} (p_{11} - p_{12})(\epsilon_{33} - \epsilon_{22})$$

- Create parameterised model – vary h , t , w , and δx to vary geometry

- FEA – model fibre under 5 bar hydrostatic pressure (proxy for out of plane strain)

- Centre of fibre cross-section ($x, y = (0,0)$) ideal for waveguide placement

- High birefringence
- Spatially suitable

Result from 5 bar hydrostatic pressure FEA: ($\epsilon_{33} - \epsilon_{22}$)

Parametric study: sensitivity to geometry

Objective:

Quantify how sensitive birefringence is to variations in each geometric parameter.

Statistical method:

- All input parameters and the birefringence response are normalized [0, 1]

- A linear regression model is fitted:

$$\text{Normalised Birefringence} = \sum_i (\text{Coefficient}_i \times \text{Normalised Parameter}_i)$$

- Regression coefficients indicate **relative sensitivity**:

- Larger absolute values = stronger influence
- Positive vs negative = direction of effect

Key takeaway: Sensitivity is enhanced in high aspect ratio, thin-walled sensors

Integration into composite materials

Hot press: Easy fibre optic egress – rapid sensor development.

- Applications:
 - Cure monitoring and producing integrated sensor laminates
- 100 kN Test Machine
 - Displacement and load-control modes.
 - Compression grips for attaching tooling.
- Heated Tooling
 - Cavity dimensions: **84 mm × 140 mm × 10 mm** (W × L × D).
 - Embedded thermocouple slots positioned 0.5 mm below surface.
 - Small egress holes for thermocouples and optical fibres.
- Watlow EZ-Zone PID Temp Control
 - 2 tool embedded control thermocouples for PID feedback.
 - Data logging for up to 8 laminate thermocouples
- Fibre Optic Interrogation
 - SmartFibre FBG sensors (standard FBG strain sensors).
 - μ HARFF FBG sensors (pressure-sensitive Fabry–Pérot type).

